

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KAFERE****FIRST NAME: CHANCELAR****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following statements is correct concerning the structure and format of the academic essay?

- The introduction moves from specific to general by stating the answer, summarizing key points, and stating a final broad statement about possible implications and/or future direction for research.
- The body, the longest part of the essay, consists of paragraphs presenting all details and arguments answering the essay question.¹**
- The conclusion should provide a general background to a topic, narrow it down to a specific theme, and summarize the essay.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 10.

- Every essay must contain a recommendations section, which is the longest part of the essay.
2. Which of the following is true about British and American English?
- British and American English are similar and can be used interchangeably in the same academic essay.
- Authors following the Turabian style must use British English.
- The same words may have different meanings between American and British English.²**
- British English is more dominant than American English.
3. Which of the following is true about referencing and plagiarism?
- Some academic essays do not need to contain references.
- Properly citing the source of information does not help in avoiding plagiarism.
- Authors do not need to cite sources of information if they paraphrase well.
- Authors do not need to cite sources when the information they are writing about is common knowledge.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 26.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 37.

4. Which of the following statements about the kinds of literature review and literature sources is true?

- A literature review can only start after formulating the research question and hypothesis.
- Secondary sources of literature provide firsthand evidence.
- Tertiary literature sources can be used in the early stages of research to get a broad overview of the topic but should not be relied on and cited to support scholarly arguments.⁴**
- Libraries are no longer helpful as sources of literature because all literature sources are readily accessible online.

5. Which statement about writing an academic paper is correct?

- Authors write the first draft for themselves to work on it to develop a final draft for readers.⁵**
- Reading through your draft academic essays does not help improve them, but reading and feedback from other readers.
- Authors must accept all comments coming from experienced reviewers or researchers.
- Some software can be used to edit draft academic essays, negating the need for human reading and editing.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 37.

⁵ Turabian, 106.

6. Which of the following is correct concerning spelling in academic writing?
- Word processor applications have spell-check features that detect all errors, and authors do not need to proofread their work.
 - According to the Turabian Rule of style, authors should use British English spellings.
 - When writing a dissertation, class essay, or any academic document, specific spelling requirements from the university precede recommendations in the Turabian Style guide.⁶**
 - Authors should not waste time consulting dictionaries when in doubt, as spell checkers will correct spellings for them.
7. Which of the following is correct about components of a dissertation research?
- A concept paper is a detailed dissertation research outline built upon the dissertation prospectus.
 - A dissertation manuscript is a concise research proposal that contains the main ideas and outlines the plan for the dissertation.
 - A dissertation prospectus is prepared for publication in a peer-reviewed journal, monograph, book, or chapter.
 - The dissertation is the final presentation of the design, execution, results, and interpretation of the research planned in the dissertation prospectus.⁷**

⁶ Turabian, 303–4.

⁷ James P Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second ed (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 4.

8. Which of the following is correct about the introduction chapter of a dissertation?
- The first part of the introduction chapter is the social significance section, which expresses the actual benefit for society in seeking a solution to the dissertation research problem.
 - The introduction starts with elements of literature that align with the research questions posed and answered in the dissertation.⁸**
 - The statement of the problem should follow immediately after the research questions.
 - A dissertation should have one research question it answers regardless of the nature of the research.
9. Which of the following is correct about the structure of a dissertation?
- A 'limitations of the study' section is included in the introduction chapter to explain the constraints to interpreting dissertation findings.
 - A chapter of the dissertation presenting a critical literature review of the research topic upon which the dissertation research is based is optional.
 - The methods chapter of the dissertation is where the student describes in detail the data collection and analysis procedures used to answer the research questions.⁹**

⁸ Sampson, 27.

⁹ Sampson, 34.

- In the findings chapter, the author interprets the dissertation research findings, exploring their implications for theory, practice, research, policy, and so on as applicable.

10. Which of the following is true concerning the WHO style guide?

- The WHO does not follow a single set of national practices on the use of English as it strives to communicate effectively with all its member states.¹⁰**
- WHO uses any abbreviation in its information as long as it is used and recognized in at least one member state.
- Since WHO is an intergovernmental organization that cooperates with member states worldwide, it can follow various writing styles.
- WHO recognizes the need for non-discriminatory language but does not provide any specific guidelines.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, Second ed (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 13.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.